

Unlocking Augmented Interactions in Short-lived Assembly Tasks

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Abstract. Augmented Reality (AR) has evolved over the past years, but before it is widely adopted and used in manufacturing industry, it has to overcome a number of technological challenges. Although new advancements in tracking and display technology have been a priority in recent research works, the use of accurate registration methods is not fundamental for users to understand the intent of the augmentation. Moreover, interactive visualization of contextual data in augmented spaces did not receive enough attention from the research community. In this paper, we investigate the creation of AR workspaces focused on interaction and visualization modes rather than on the registration accuracy, and how to provide more effective means to support assembly tasks in hybrid human-machine manufacturing lines. In particular, we focus on short-lived assembly tasks, i.e. manufacturing of limited batches of customized products, which do not yield significant returns considering the effort necessary to adapt AR systems and the production time frame.

Keywords: Augmented Reality, Interaction, Assembly, Manufacturing

1 Introduction

Manufacturing assembly lines are subject to a continuous fluctuation in production demands such as customization level and quantity [ELM05]. While many continuous and repetitive actions in assembly tasks can be automated to improve production efficiency, the biggest challenge to automation is when a new product variant is introduced into the production line.

The manufacturing of products variants that change in relatively short intervals is efficient when the process integrate human workers, as they adapt to new manufacturing operations without interrupting the production process. However, human workers are more prone to errors than machines. Replacing the human factor with an automated process could, perhaps, decrease the complexity of the solution. Nonetheless, maintaining the presence of human workers in the assembly chain can create a competitive advantage. This advantage comes from the fact that humans can rely on their natural senses to form very complex and intuitive, yet instant, solutions. In contrast, automated pipelines require

1 reprogramming to a new product family or manufacturing problem. A techno-
2 logical solution that provides training and assistance to workers in assembly
3 tasks could mitigate the issue of human errors and be more cost-effective than
4 reprogramming the entire system for a new product family.

5 In recent years, manufacturing industries have been pursuing solutions based
6 on augmented reality (AR) to empower their workers, actively and passively,
7 with new possibilities of perceiving information in a timely manner, e.g. about
8 assembly processes, without altering their established work routines. In this pa-
9 per, we propose an AR framework based on low cost technology that provides
10 effective means to support assembly tasks, in particular in short-lived assembly
11 tasks, i.e. manufacturing of very limited batches of customized products. Man-
12 ufacturing of products that are limited to a few units do not yield significant
13 returns to justify the effort required to adapt the AR system. We also describe
14 how to create AR user assembly manuals with minimal effort and adapt them to
15 multiple context and user profiles, e.g. different levels of worker disabilities. The
16 AR framework automatically interprets assembly diagrams and creates superim-
17 posed task-related content for assembly tasks. In our test case, we evaluate the
18 use of projection-based AR and we compare it to AR display-based approaches,
19 that often divert workers' hands and attention between digital instructions and
20 the assembly process.

21 The rest of the paper continues as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of
22 related works of AR in manufacturing processes. Section 3 describes the proposed
23 AR framework, including the required setup (Section 3.1), the procedure to
24 create AR multimedia content (Section 3.2), the tracking methodology (Section
25 3.3) and the calibration that is required to project the assembly instructions
26 on the workspace (Section 3.4). Finally, Section 4 provides a discussion and
27 enumerates future works.

28 **2 State of the art**

29 The integration of AR in industrial manufacturing processes, namely in assembly
30 tasks, has proved to reduce manufacturing errors and to ease cognitive load of
31 participants by 82% when compared to paper-based instructions, on a monitor,
32 or steadily displayed on an HMD (Head Mounted Display) [TOBM03]. Previous
33 studies also demonstrated an improvements in the performance of untrained
34 workers [FBB⁺17, Hoř15, PDTP12]. In these studies it was also observed that
35 proposed AR solutions failed to address the existent know-how of expert workers
36 and attempted to impose new routines, which led to a deterioration in their
37 performances [FBB⁺17].

38 Assembly operations typically require workers to locate assembly parts and
39 then to use their both hands either to hold or to perform the assembly task.
40 Consequently, the interaction with visual interfaces through gestures is inconve-
41 nient and indirectly shifts their attention from assembly parts. Projection-based
42 solutions have been increasingly regarded as an alternative for ubiquitous visual
43 output that can replace displays and AR smart glasses. One of the advantages

1 is that it can overcome the pitfalls of limited field-of-view found in AR glasses
2 (which makes harder to guide the worker to these parts) and can augment phys-
3 ical objects with digital content, without the need to hold any accessory or shift
4 attention between a display and the workspace.

5 In the field of industrial manufacturing, Sand et al. [SBPR16] developed a
6 prototype to project AR instructions into the physical workspace, which enabled
7 the worker not only to find the pieces but also to assemble products without prior
8 knowledge. Rodriguez et al. [RQG⁺15] proposed a similar solution in which in-
9 structions are directly overlaid with the real world using projection mapping.
10 Petersen et al. [PPS13] projected video overlays into the environment at the
11 correct position and time using a piecewise homographic transform. By display-
12 ing a color overlay of the users hands, feedback could be given without occluding
13 task-relevant objects.

14 Challenges in the visualization and interaction with projected-based systems
15 have been widely investigated. Tang et al. [TOBM03] found that occlusions of
16 objects by digital content or presenting information over a cluttered background
17 can decrease task performance. Funk et al. [FKS16] experiments demonstrated
18 that users tended to prefer instructions to not be directly projected onto the
19 actual assembly situation but peripherally beside the target region, thus not
20 occluding relevant objects. Feiner et al. [FMS93] proposed a rule-based prototype
21 to create different types of graphics for the user. However, very little efforts has
22 been taken to investigate AR systems that embed task know-how and facilitate
23 personalization towards different worker skills and disabilities.

24 **3 Solution Fundamentals**

25 Many projector-based prototypes have been created to project content on arbi-
26 trary surfaces. However, most of these works failed to consider the interaction
27 with assembly parts that pose challenges to computer vision algorithms. Other
28 works have solved the problem by employing expensive technology such as 3D
29 cameras to track and interact with objects in projected spaces. In this section,
30 we introduce the concepts that enable us to transfer the interaction space from
31 the conventional desktop space to the direct interaction in the physical space,
32 i.e. where the projected displays are located. Our solution aims to deliver a ro-
33 bust and low cost tracking system for the assembly of electric cabinets, which
34 involves assembly parts that pose great challenges to modern computer vision
35 algorithms. Another advantage in our solution is the minimal amount time that
36 is required to deploy new digital assembly manuals that take into consideration
37 worker skills and disabilities.

38 **3.1 Enabling Technology and Setup**

39 Assembly operations often require workers to hold assembly parts or to use both
40 hands to perform assembly sub-tasks. Consequently, hand-based interaction with
41 visual interfaces is inconvenient and affects their attention. In this section, we

1 describe an AR framework that provides graphical instructions projected or
2 overlaid on top of physical components. The proposed use case requires workers
3 to assembly an electric cabinet. In particular, we focus on the task of cable wiring
4 the cabinet.

5 Our framework supports assembly of electric cabinets with two different ap-
6 plications. The first application helps users to design AR assembly manuals for
7 new product families, see workflow in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Ingestion and creation of AR applications

8 The application consists of a web-based interface that can ingest electrical
9 schematics or drawings in DWG or DXF format, as well Excel files describing
10 the assembly process of a given product. In real assembly processes, this material
11 is printed to hard copies and delivered to workers. Hence, the effort required to
12 create new AR applications is limited to assigning a location to the AR content.
13 The task can be performed in-situ using the projectors as display or remotely
14 through a web browser that depicts a video camera streaming of the physical
15 location and the digital content, see last step in Fig. 1.

16 The second application provides real-time projection-based instructions to
17 the worker. The proposed framework also relies on a rule-based decision system
18 to adapt the AR experience to workers with disabilities. The use of a rule-based
19 decision system simplifies significantly the design of digital assembly manuals be-
20 cause it reduces human-machine interaction to an event-consequence metaphor,
21 which in turn reduces the complexity of programming workflow. Moreover, it
22 allows digital assembly manuals to be automatically customized by external
23 sensors and worker processes. As part of this application, we have developed a
24 robust approach for the detection of assembly parts that lack of textural infor-
25 mation. Tracking assembly parts is necessity to superimpose content and force
26 certain elements to be in free spaces. The user interaction, requires workers to
27 use bracelets with printed markers to enable the framework to estimate their 3D
28 hands pose without the requirement of a 3D camera, see Fig. 2. Our approach

1 has the advantage that it works from a single camera perspective and benefits
2 from usability at the workspace and tracking speed, hence maintaining good
3 levels of interaction feedback.

Fig. 2: Setup and AR prototype

4 To summarize, our framework is built on top of a distributed network archi-
5 tecture, which defines mechanisms to automatically adapt the AR experience to
6 different hardware configurations, e.g. the use of multiple projectors to reduce
7 projection occlusions by physical materials or irregular surfaces, see Fig. 2. The
8 setup consists of a table, which corresponds to the workspace, fixing brackets
9 that hold a camera in zenith position (it is a low cost web camera, configured
10 to capture at 640×480 resolution), bracelets with printed markers to track user
11 hand with robustness, and two conventional projectors fixed in strategical aerial
12 positions to cover different projection areas, see Fig. 2.

13 3.2 Interaction Context and Focus

14 To obtain an easy-to-use interaction concept, we kept the set of visual inter-
15 action elements and gestures as limited as possible. Interaction gestures were

1 constrained to touch of projected UI and the tracking technology limited to low
2 cost cameras, as described in the previous section.

3 When the operator places the base of an electric cabinet on the table, the
4 system automatically identifies the object by processing the images captured by
5 the camera and starts projecting AR instructions on the table to help the worker
6 with the assembly task (installation of wiring in the electrical cabinet). Track-
7 ing assembly parts is very important because as observed in previous studies,
8 workers might prefer certain types of content not to be projected over the com-
9 ponents. Hence, we need to ensure that projected content is re-adapted when
10 assembly parts might move over it. In the following sections, we describe the
11 techniques used for the identification of the object, detection of gestures, and
12 for the projection of multimedia content.

13 The detection of users gestures, e.g. touches in projected elements, requires
14 the worker to wear bracelets to estimate the 3D hand pose. Our approach miti-
15 gates existing limitations in tracking approaches, linked to issues in industrial
16 environments like magnetism and luminosity, and can estimate the probability
17 of touching projected elements on the physical surface with a low cost solution.
18 In Fig. 2 we can find the design of the reusable bracelets, which are designed
19 to not affect workers' ergonomics. In future work, bracelets could be used also
20 to encode the user identity, which would simplify aspects in collaborations that
21 involve multiple workers with different disabilities.

22 As mentioned in previous sections, interaction context and focus is inferred
23 by a rule-based engine that analyses the state of each device and sensor partic-
24 ipating in the AR experience (e.g. two computers that control two projectors,
25 tracking module, worker skills and disabilities, and service providing AR in-
26 structions). The main advantage of our configuration is that it simplifies the
27 initial design of the digital assembly manual, which is automatically enriched
28 with content that depends on sensor feedback and worker profiles. For example,
29 our framework can interact with third-party workload schedulers to generate
30 rules that reprogram workflow of projected-based content to a specific worker,
31 i.e. task context. The same approach can be apply to personalize projected el-
32 ements to different worker's profiles. The rule-based model is build separately
33 from the system that provides AR instructions and can be personalized through
34 a web interface or controlled with an API. The rules could eventually be main-
35 tained in real-time by computational modules that observe the assembly process
36 at different granularities. The definition of the rules take the form of:

$$37 \text{ Rules } \begin{cases} r_1: \text{Device.UserID} = \text{'bsimoes'} \rightarrow \text{Execute.AppID} = \text{'App1'} \\ r_2: \text{Text.Color} = \text{red} \ \& \ \text{User.Protanopia} \rightarrow \text{Text.Color} = \text{cyan} \end{cases}$$

38 The entire framework is event-driven and uses JSON notation for all com-
39 munications. The rule syntax takes the type of messages exchanged through the
40 network and asserts on their JSON attributes.

41 In Fig. 2 we can visualize in the lower left corner, the worker interacting
42 with projected elements and in the lower right corner the content adopting a
43 new location due to a translation of the electric cabinet.

3.3 Tracking of Assembly Parts

The setup of the system, in which the camera is in a zenith position and the object (the electric cabinet) moves in a table whose plane is parallel to the camera's image, enable us to simplify the problem of detection and tracking to an image warping (the idea is similar to the one applied when mapping aerial photographs). Instead of using the 3D model of the object as input (which is not always available and its creation is time consuming), we only take an aerial photo of it to extract all required data. This aerial image is used as a reference, hence the problem of the camera pose can be modeled by a homography, which is a transformation that moves points from one plane (camera image) to another plane (reference image).

The electrical cabinet that is shown in Fig. 2 is an object that is difficult to detect in an image, especially when the camera is low cost and does not offer a high quality image. The electrical cabinet has poor texture, and therefore, the well known texture-based techniques (particularly those that use feature points and descriptors [HAA16]) are not well suited. However, it does have predominant edges that can be used to perform the detection based on its shape. Given that, the detection is solved by applying a similarity measure that matches the edges directions of the electrical cabinet extracted in a reference image with those extracted in the current input camera image. In an offline step, given a reference image of the electrical box, the edges and their directions are extracted. Thus, in an online stage, the reference edge model is tested throughout all the positions of the input camera image (in a coarse to fine mode to reduce the computational cost and make it close to real-time) and the position with the highest similarity is returned (Fig. 3). Moreover, to achieve rotation and scale invariance, the reference image is rotated and scaled (columns and rows of the offline step of Fig. 3, respectively) with different rotation and scale steps, and several reference models are created (one for each rotation-scale combination). See [Ste01] for more details. Although this technique is not robust against viewpoint changes, we do not suffer this weakness, as the camera is in zenith position and the electrical cabinet only moves on a table, i.e., the viewpoint change is minimal.

Once the electrical cabinet has been detected in the current frame, its position has to be updated in subsequent frames, i.e, it has to be tracked. *Tracking*, unlike *detection*, exploits information from previous frames to update the current location of the object. Thus, for example, the positioning problem, instead of covering the entire image, is restricted to only an area close to the position of the previous frame. This *temporal coherence* assumption simplifies the problem, and due to this, techniques that we discarded for detection have been demonstrated suitable for tracking. This is the case of the optical flow of some feature points [yB00]. We have observed that it is possible to extract a few interest points on the surface of the electrical cabinet, enough to apply the optical flow and get an initial estimation of the position.

The optical flow technique is robust against fast movements, but it accumulates error and suffers from drift. To overcome this problem, the position estimation given by the optical flow is refined using an edge tracker [DC02] (Fig.

Fig. 3: Detection and tracking pipelines. The colors of the edge pattern represent different gradient directions. See text for more details.

3). The input reference image of the electrical cabinet is also processed here in an offline step to extract some reference edges (those that have strong response). Then, during the online execution, these reference edges are positioned using the initial estimation of the optical flow and their presence in the current frame is measured to minimize the error between prior and current positioning and achieve more accuracy.

Additionally, we have included a keyframe tracker to recover from errors of the other two trackers described above. When the electrical cabinet is detected, that frame is used as keyframe, extracting some feature points and descriptors. In this way, when a new camera frame is received, its feature points and descriptors are computed and matched with those of the keyframe (a similar approach is described in [CC10]). When good enough matches are found, the position of the electrical cabinet can be recovered in the current frame. The recovery strategy is applied only when we detect a long displacement of the box (10 pixels in our case) or when the optical flow has been degraded (20% of feature points have been lost)(Fig. 3). This keyframe tracker allows us to avoid having to switch to the *detection* state in some occasions, whose processing is more expensive computationally. Furthermore, we have noticed that this keyframe tracker grants more robustness in case of a partial occlusion of the electric cabinet, especially when the operator uses his/her hand to place a component into the cabinet.

3.4 Projection Mapping and Spatial Calibration

The projection of multimedia content at a desirable location, when observed through a camera from a random angle, requires us to find a transformation that moves points from the camera's image to the projector's space. Although this task could be done manually, we have automatized the calibration process in our solution. Assuming the camera and projector are calibrated independently, it consists in a sequential projection of a chess pattern along the entire projection area (a table in our case), such that each projection of the pattern is detected in

1 the image of the camera. Therefore, it is possible to find the camera-projector
2 relation (or vice versa, since the problem is analogous). Our implementation
3 is similar to the solution described in [MT12]. It is also noteworthy that we
4 have modeled the transformation between the camera and the projector using a
5 homography, which is a valid simplification because the multimedia content is
6 projected on the table, which is a plane.

7 Once both devices are calibrated and the camera pose is known (Section 3.3),
8 the projection of the multimedia content is straightforward. Let H_{ref}^{cam} be the
9 homography that transform points from the reference image of the object to the
10 current camera image, and let H_{cam}^{proj} be the homography that relates the camera
11 image with the projector image that is projected. Then, the multimedia content
12 that has been positioned in the reference image (M_{ref}) is projected in the desired
13 location using the following transformation composition: $H_{cam}^{proj} * H_{ref}^{cam} * M_{ref}$

14 4 Discussion and Conclusions

15 In this paper, we propose a projection-based AR framework to augment assem-
16 bly workspaces that require the interpretation of electrical schematics. Workers'
17 disabilities were considered in the definition of how the AR system interacts. The
18 advantages of our work include fast creation and personalization of projection-
19 based assembly instructions to different humans skills, which is critical to in-
20 dustries that have to deal with high product customization and short product
21 life cycles. Our solution overcomes drawbacks in 2D tracking technology, and
22 does not require multiple cameras to track and find 3D projection coordinates
23 in arbitrary surfaces.

24 In our preliminary tests, the creation of digital manuals from electrical schemat-
25 ics took between 0 up to 10 seconds per instruction. The time required considered
26 minor changes to projected elements and definition of relevant rules. The frame-
27 work did not require adaptation of existent assembly materials to the framework
28 and facilitated the adaptation of the manual to different worker's skills. Hence,
29 improving the time needed to create manuals and to assemble electric cabinets.

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